

Studies in Possible Oral Hypoglycemic Agents. Part III.* Synthesis of Some 3-Amino-5-phenyl- and 5-Amino-3-methyl-1,2,4-thiadiazole Derivatives

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Several 3-methyl- and 5-phenyl-1,2,4-thiadiazoles, carrying substituted amino functions in the 5- and 3-positions, have been prepared as potential hypoglycemic agents.

The discovery of the hypoglycemic activity in 2-(*p*-aminobenzenesulphonamido)-5-isopropyl-1,3,4-thiadiazole (I.P.T.D.) by Janbon and co-workers¹ has led to an intensive study of variously substituted 1,3,4-thiadiazoles. It was suggested earlier² that the activity of these thiadiazoles as well as that of the subsequently introduced sulphonylureas and the biguanides was associated with the presence, in their molecules, of a urea, thiourea, or a guanidino moiety. The support received for this hypothesis during preliminary testing experiments on rats³ prompted us to study the isomeric 1,2,4-thiadiazoles. The chemistry of these compounds has been probed only recently by Kurzer *et al.*⁴ and Goerdeler and co-workers⁵. Preliminary testing of 3,5-diamino-1,2,4-thiadiazole and 5-amino-3-(*p*-toluenesulphonamido)-1,2,4-thiadiazole indicates that these compounds possess interesting hypoglycemic activity and low toxicity (A. K. Roy, personal communication). It was therefore considered of interest to introduce sulphonamido and urea moieties into the 1,2,4-thiadiazole nucleus at suitable positions with a view to testing these compounds for hypoglycemic activity. The following types of 1,2,4-thiadiazoles were accordingly prepared.

3-Methyl-5-(*p*-toluenesulphonamido)-1,2,4-thiadiazole was prepared by condensing 5-amino-3-methyl-1,2,4-thiadiazole⁶ with the appropriate sulphonyl chloride⁶. The *p*-nitrobenzoyl derivative (I: R' = *p*-NO₂C₆H₄CO-) was prepared by allowing the corresponding aminothiadiazole to react with *p*-nitrobenzoyl chloride in acetone in presence

*Part II, Dhar, Popli, and Dhar, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1961, 20C, 145.

1. *Montpellier Med.*, 1942, 21, 489.

2. Paul *et al.*, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1959, 19C, 21.

3. Roy *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1960, 19C, 75.

4. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 1.

5. *Chem. Ber.*, 1954, 87, 57.

6. Farbenfabriken Bayer, Akt.-Ges, B.P. 830, 316/1960; *Chem. Abs.*, 1961, 55, 571.

of pyridine; the 5-(3-phenylureido) compound (I:R' = C₆H₅NHCO) was obtained in excellent yield by the usual procedure, using phenyl isocyanate in dry acetone. For the preparation of the compound (II), the intermediate ethyl *N*-(5-phenyl-1,2,4-thiadiazol-3-yl)-carbamate, which could not be prepared by the condensation of 3-amino-5-phenyl-1,2,4-thiadiazole with ethyl chloroformate in acetone, chloroform, or dimethylformamide containing anhydrous potassium carbonate or in absolute ethanol containing sodium ethoxide, was obtained in 75% yield by the condensation of 3-amino-5-phenyl-1,2,4-thiadiazole with an excess of ethyl chloroformate at 120°. The carbamate, so obtained, was condensed with suitable amines to yield the desired thiadiazole ureas (II).

The sulphonylurea derivatives of 5-phenyl-1,2,4-thiadiazole (III) were prepared by the interaction of the appropriate carbamates of sulphonamides and 3-amino-5-phenyl-1,2,4-thiadiazole.

The compounds, now reported, are being tested for possible hypoglycemic activity and the findings will be reported later.

EXPERIMENTAL

3-Methyl-5-(*p*-toluenesulphonamido)-1,2,4-thiadiazole (Sl. No. 28).—*p*-Toluenesulphonyl chloride (3.3 g.) was added to a solution of 5-amino-3-methyl-1,2,4-thiadiazole (2 g.) in pyridine (10.5 ml) and the mixture kept overnight. Pyridine was then distilled under vacuum and the residue treated cautiously with 10% HCl when a small quantity of a gummy mass separated which was filtered. On further acidification of the filtrate, a precipitate was obtained which on recrystallisation from ethanol furnished the product, melting at 223-24°. (Found: N, 15.95. C₁₀H₁₁O₃N₃S₂ requires N, 15.62%).

3-Methyl-5-(*p*-nitrobenzamido)-1,2,4-thiadiazole (Sl. No. 29).—A mixture of 5-amino-3-methyl-1,2,4-thiadiazole (0.9 g.), *p*-nitrobenzoyl chloride (1.5 g.), and pyridine (0.7 g.) was refluxed in acetone solution for 3 hours. After removal of the solvent at reduced pressure, the residue was treated with 10% HCl and the precipitate recrystallised from acetone, m.p. 289°. (Found: N, 21.39. C₁₀H₉O₃N₃S requires N, 21.22%).

3-Methyl-5-(3'-phenylureido)-1,2,4-thiadiazole (Sl. No. 30).—Phenyl isocyanate (2 g.) was added gradually to a solution of 5-amino-3-methyl-1,2,4-thiadiazole (2 g.) in minimum quantity of dry acetone and the mixture kept at 40° for 1 hour. On addition with water, the reaction mixture gave a white precipitate which was subsequently crystallised from isopropanol-water, m.p. 250°. (Found: N, 23.97. C₁₀H₁₀ON₃S requires N, 23.93%).

Ethyl *N*-(5-Phenyl-1,2,4-thiadiazol-3-yl)carbamate.—3-Amino-5-phenyl-1,2,4-thiadiazole was mixed intimately with excess of ethyl chloroformate and the mixture heated gradually to 120°. The temperature was maintained for 4 hours, followed by removal of the unchanged ethyl chloroformate under reduced pressure. On crystallisation from ethanol, the residue gave the product, m.p. 119°, in 75% yield. (Found: C, 53.22; H, 4.77; N, 16.64. C₁₁H₁₁O₂N₃S requires C, 53.02; H, 4.42; N, 16.86%).

5-Phenyl-3-substituted-ureido-1,2,4-thiadiazoles (Sl. No. 31-48).—In the general preparative procedure, an intimate mixture of the above carbamate, the appropriate amine (1:2.5 molar ratio), and a few drops of pyridine was heated at 120° for 3 to 4 hours. Pyridine and most of the unchanged amine were subsequently removed under reduced pressure and the residue was treated with cold dilute hydrochloric acid; the resulting thiadiazole crystallised from ethanol. $\gamma\gamma$ -Diethylaminopropylureido derivative was, however, isolated as hydrochloride and recrystallised from isopropanol. In the reactions in which 2-, 3-, and 4-amino-pyridines were employed, the residue was simply washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol. The compounds prepared in this series are reported in Table I.

TABLE I
(Vide structure II)

Sl. No.	R [*] .	M.P. [*]	Formula.	% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.		% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
31	Butyl ¹⁰	112-13°	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ ON ₄ S	56.51	56.52	6.18	5.90	20.49	20.29
32	Amyl ¹¹	78°	C ₁₄ H ₁₈ ON ₄ S	58.27	57.93	6.56	6.20	18.94	19.28
33	Hexyl ¹⁰	80.5-90°	C ₁₅ H ₂₀ ON ₄ S	59.39	59.21	6.54	6.58	18.06	18.42
34	Phenyl	180°	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ ON ₄ S	61.04	60.81	4.45	4.54	18.71	18.92
35	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	189-90°	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ ON ₄ S	62.28	61.93	4.89	4.51	18.16	18.06
36	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	155.5°	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₄ S	..	..	..	..	16.77	17.18
37	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	171°	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₄ S	..	..	..	..	16.86	17.18
38	2-Phenylethyl	155°	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ ON ₄ S	63.33	62.96	5.23	4.94	17.42	17.28
39	4-Pyridyl	233°	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ ON ₅ S	58.66	58.56	4.25	3.70	23.59	23.57
40	2-Pyridyl	176°	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ ON ₅ S	58.90	58.56	3.96	3.70	23.95	23.57
41	3-Pyridyl	228°	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ ON ₅ S	..	..	..	..	23.53	23.57
42	4-Chloro-2-pyridyl	226°	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ ON ₅ ClS	50.91	50.67	2.91	3.01	20.35	21.11
43	Cyclohexyl	160°	C ₁₅ H ₁₈ ON ₄ S	59.88	59.60	6.35	5.96	19.01	18.66
44	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	174.5-75°	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ ON ₄ ClS	54.34	54.49	3.62	3.32	16.64	16.94
45	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	211°	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ ON ₄ ClS	54.63	54.49	3.70	3.32	16.86	16.94
46	3-Diethylaminopropyl hydrochloride	182-84°	C ₁₆ H ₂₄ ON ₅ ClS	51.83	51.96	6.76	6.49	18.98	19.94
47	Ethoxycarbonyl-methyl	184°	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₄ S	..	..	..	..	18.64	18.30
48	Anilino	215°	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ ON ₅ S	..	..	..	..	22.34	22.51

* the melting points are uncorrected.

3-(3'-Arylsulphonylureido)-5-phenyl-1,2,4-thiadiazoles (Sl. No. 49-53).—A suspension of 3-amino-5-phenyl-1,2,4-thiadiazole in benzene was treated with an equimolar quantity of the appropriate aryl sulphonyl urethanes^{8,9} and the mixture was refluxed to a clear solution. The solvent was removed under vacuum and the residue heated at 120°/4mm for 4 hours. The residue was purified subsequently by refluxing successively with ethanol, ethyl acetate, and chloroform. The final product, which did not dissolve in any of these solvents, was obtained in a crystalline form.

8. Marshall *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1958, **23**, 927.

9. Cassady *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1958, **23**, 923.

In the case of *p*-toluenesulphonyl and benzenesulphonyl derivatives, the products were finally recrystallised from ethyl acetate. Compounds prepared in this series are reported in Table II.

TABLE II
(Vide structure III)

Sl. No.	R ¹ .	M.P.*	Formula.	% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.		% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
49	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	202-203°	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₃ N ₄ S ₂	51.32	51.33	3.92	3.74	14.72	14.87
50	Phenyl	209-10°	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₃ N ₄ S ₂	49.77	50.00	3.87	3.34	15.65	15.53
51	4-Acetamidophenyl	229-30°	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₄ N ₄ S ₂	48.00	48.92	3.99	3.59	16.65	16.78
52	4-Chlorophenyl	212°	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ O ₃ N ₄ Cl ₂ S ₂	..	..	..	..	14.38	14.20
53	3,4-Dichlorophenyl	213°	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₃ N ₄ Cl ₂ S ₂	..	..	..	..	12.76	13.05

*All the melting points are uncorrected.

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